

FABRICATION OF ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH POWDERS AND CERAMIC PREFORMS BY A CENTRIFUGAL PROCESS

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1 Introduction

The proper selection of components (matrix and reinforcement materials) and also the physical and chemical phenomena occurring in technological processes has significant affect on properties of composite materials [1,2]. The main processes for manufacturing of Al-MMCs at industrial scale may be classified into two basic groups: solid state processes and liquid state processes. In the case of liquid state methods the wetting phenomena in ceramic-metal system are very important [3]. Whereas, the composite structure is formed during the solidification process, which depends on the conditions and parameters of the casting process [4]. In recent years there have been many papers concerning the possibility of manufacturing functionally graded composites, and composites with local distribution of the reinforcement [5-7]. The centrifugal casting process has many specific advantages. First of all this is one of effective methods of about low cost production of special castings with graded structure and properties. Therefore it has many applications in manufacturing industry today. Interaction the centrifugal force during centrifugal casting of composite suspension provides the local distribution of the reinforcement in the cast [5].

The aim of investigations is infiltration of the porous preforms at the pressure in centrifugal casting process. Make an assumption that the porous preforms will be create the reinforcement layer in specific area of the casting. In turn, casting of composite suspensions under the same conditions will allow obtain different functionally graded structure in the cast.

This paper present only a fragment of investigations conducted by article's authors on the use of casting methods for the production of functional metal matrix composites (mechanical stirring, centrifugal casting, gas pressures infiltration - GPI) [1,2].

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Centrifugal casting processes

For manufacture of composite materials have been used on the equipment (Fig. 1) designed and constructed at the Silesian University of Technology as the part of scientific work financed by National Science Centre (project number: N N508 630 540).

Fig. 1. View of the experimental system for fabrication of Al-MMCs by the centrifugal casting process at the Silesian University of Technology.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. The experimental system for fabrication of Al-MMCs by the use of centrifugal casting process: a) view of casting chamber and rotating mould, b) 3D model of the rotating mould.

The aluminium composite suspensions with 5% vol. of silicon carbide (SiCp/AlSi12CuMgNi) were manufactured by the stir casting method in argon atmosphere and the next poured into the graphite moulds (Fig.3), [1].

Fig. 3. View of composite ingots manufactured by the stir casting method.

The next all composite ingots were remolded in the crucible furnace and poured into centrifugal casting mould at 4200 rpm. The rotating mould was preheated at 250°C. The pouring temperature range of composite suspension was 720-740°C. On the Figures 4a and 4b are presented images of cast composite obtained by the centrifugal casting process. Moreover in the investigations described in this article the centrifugal force resulting from rotation of the mould were used to infiltration of the Al₂O₃ ceramic perform by molten alloy (Fig. 4c). The centrifugal infiltration process was conducted with the same conditions like in the process of centrifugal casting composite suspensions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Images of cast composite obtained by the centrifugal casting process: a) view of composite cast with feed system, b) cross-section of cast obtained in the centrifugal casting of composite suspension, c) cross-section of cast obtained in the centrifugal infiltration of porous perform by the molten aluminium alloy.

The structure of composite samples obtained at the centrifugal process was characterized by means of light (LM) and scanning microscopy (SEM) methods. The phase and chemical compositions of

the reinforcement were identified by diffraction and X-ray spectroscopy methods.

2.2 Structure of component materials

The eutectic EN AC- AlSi12CuMgNi aluminium alloy were used as the matrix for all prepared composites. Figure 5a illustrates the light microscope images of the base aluminium alloy, which was used to prepare composites. The AlSi12CuMgNi base alloy have been modified by 1%Mg and 0.03% Sr additions (Fig. 5b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Microstructure of AlSi12CuMgNi alloys in the cast state, LM: a) before modification, b) after modification by 1% Mg and 0.03% Sr additions.

The magnesium added to improve the wettability between matrix and reinforcement. Addition of 0.03% strontium were used to changes the size and morphology of the Al-Si eutectic grains.

The silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) with an average size of 20-40 μm were used as reinforcement of AlSi12CuMgNi aluminium alloy. The image of SiC particles morphology presented on Figure 6. The porous Al_2O_3 ceramics was performed in the Institute of Ceramics and Building Materials in Warsaw [2]. The Al_2O_3 preform is characterized by the slight gradient of pore size from about 200 μm to 700 μm . The macrostructure and microstructure of Al_2O_3 preform are shown in the Figures 7 and 8.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. The morphology of SiC powders used as reinforcement of aluminium matrix alloy, SEM.

Fig. 7. The macrostructure of Al_2O_3 preform used to infiltration by the liquid metal in the centrifugal process.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. SEM images of porous Al_2O_3 ceramic preform.

The volume fraction of the ceramics phase were approximately 40 vol.%. The remaining area of preform (60 vol.%) could be filled up with liquid aluminium matrix alloy.

Fig. 9. The chemical composition in area 1 from the porous Al_2O_3 ceramic preform which presents the figure 8.

3 Results

The selected, representative microstructure of the investigated composites obtained using by centrifugal casting method are presented in Figures 10-14.

Fig. 10. The macrostructure of composite obtained by centrifugal infiltration of porous Al_2O_3 ceramics by liquid aluminium alloy.

(b)

(a)

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Microstructure of composite obtained by centrifugal infiltration of porous Al_2O_3 ceramics by liquid aluminium alloy: a) LM image, b) SEM image.

Fig. 12. Image of cross-section of the cast obtained by the centrifugal casting of $\text{AlSi12CuMgNi/SiC}_p$ composite suspension and areas in which the microscopic observation were performed..

(c)

Fig. 13. Microstructure of $\text{AlSi12CuMgNi/SiC}_p$ composite obtained by the centrifugal casting and distribution of SiC particles in the aluminium matrix: a) in area 1, b) in are 2, c) in area 3.

Three areas of composite were investigated: the central (area 2) and two opposite areas near the edge of as-cast sample (area 1 and area 2), (Fig. 12). Analyzed surface of composite was ground and polished.

Fig. 14. LM micrograph of AlSi12CuMgNi/SiC_p composite microstructure showing connection between SiC particles and Al alloy matrix.

4 Summary of results

The preliminary investigation presented in the article proved that centrifugal casting process can be used to fabrication of composite materials about functional structure. As shown in composite fabricated via pressure centrifugal infiltration process of Al₂O₃ ceramic preforms by the molten aluminium alloy the pores are almost fully filled by the aluminium alloy (Figs. 10,11). Basic microscopic investigations revealed good joints between the porous preform and the aluminium matrix alloy (Fig. 11).

Whereas the samples obtained by the pouring of composite suspension into centrifugal casting mould at 4200 rpm characterized uniform structure about minimal porosity both in the central area (area 2) and the area 3 (Figs. 12 and 13 b,c). In these areas the casting defects were not observed. Microscopic observation using light microscopy techniques revealed good joint between the SiC particles and the aluminium matrix alloy. In the outer region identified slightly increased porosity and the clusters of particles (Fig. 12,13a).

For a full evaluation of the quality of the connection between components in produced composites (ceramic preforms-Al alloy matrix and SiC ceramic particles-Al alloy matrix) are needed the detailed studies using advanced methods to assess the structure.

Further work carried out in the described area will be published in the next articles. Further planned research will be focused on influence of technological parameters on the structure and properties of composites produced by the semi-centrifugal casting method and the via centrifugal infiltration process.

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